

Quantum Zero Point Energy and Lorentz Invariants Part II

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In Part I we noted that in quantum mechanics, and even in the case of special relativity, there is an arbitrariness associated with x and t . For example, momentum in one dimension is exactly 0. One cannot arbitrarily shift it. If $x=0$, however, this is arbitrary, it may be shifted. We argued that this arbitrariness and the independence of x and t in a rest frame m_0 , $x=0$, $t=t_0$ should carry over into the results seen in a moving frame, but in that case $x'/t'=v$ because a Lorentz transformation links $(x=0, t=0)$ to $(x'=0, t'=0)$. Thus it appears that the arbitrariness of x, t and their independence have been broken, but we argue that a special Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ restores it by creating a time period \hbar/E and wavelength \hbar/p . In other words, a mathematical point is an abstraction representing a wavelength region defined by p through a complex probability $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. the wavefunction (and a similar $\exp(-iEt)$ for time).

In this note, we focus on these points in further detail. A point x is associated with p or $-p$ in one dimension, but a distribution, say $\cos(px)$, combines a fixed p with probabilities and gives the impression of positive and negative momentum values when the slope is positive or negative. Thus $\cos(px)$ by itself shows no overall translational motion, but contains regions of positive or negative momentum i.e. zero point motion. One must superimpose on this zero point motion (which exists for all energies) actual "translation" to the right or left. Given that positive and negative p 's already exist in one dimension which have nothing to do with translation, one is forced to move into a second dimension to create the translational motion which is associated with a probability such that each x point has the same value. This then leads to $\exp(ipx)$.

Next we consider a bound state situation. In the case of $\exp(ipx)$, $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ are linked to the positive/negative zero point type energy which has nothing to do with translation, while p has everything to do with translational motion. Thus if one is only interested in the translational motion (as Newton was) one may map $\exp(ipx)$ to p at x . An interesting feature, however, that appears in quantum mechanics is that is the zero point type motion which creates a very specific kind of averaging combines with $pp/2m$ values to create the notion of translation (to the right and left at the same time so to speak because time is removed from the bound problem. This is very different from the quantum free particle which has p and $pp/2m$ at each x point and is due to the two dimensional nature of $\exp(ipx)$ which leads to $p\exp(ipx) - p\exp(-px)$ not equal 0. Thus the nature of "acceleration" in a bound quantum system is closely linked to zero point energy (i.e. the back and forth action-reaction momentum) which is already present in a free particle. In fact, for a bound system, this zero type motion is linked to the average $-i\hbar dW/dx / W$ (W =wavefunction) which is not the same as $prms(x)$ obtained from $-1/2m d/dx dW/dx / W$.

Two Sets of Positive/Negative Scales and Two Dimensions in $\exp(ipx)$

In Part I, we argued there exists a certain independence and arbitrariness to x and t which is not present in $x(t)$, a deterministic expression. This may be seen in special relativity. A rest system m_0 , $x=0$, $t=t_0$ (with x and t chosen in a completely independent and arbitrary fashion) leads to $x'/t'=v$ when seen in a moving frame. In the rest frame, p momentum =0 and there is no

arbitrariness to this. Furthermore E and p are not independent because $p=Ev$. The relation $x=vt$ should really be $dx/dt=v$. We argued that one may restore independence and arbitrariness to a certain degree by considering the special Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ which remains unchanged for x',t' and $x'+\hbar/p$ and $t'+\hbar/E$. Thus we consider a spatial distribution with a wavelength \hbar/p (and a similar notion for time).

We argue that this means that it is not a point x which is associated with p (except in an average way), but a region of the length of a wavelength \hbar/p which depends on the magnitude of p . We argue that a symmetric distribution exists with the wavelength as its base.

We note that a distribution which has the appearance of a $\sin(px)$ or $\cos(px)$ hump has positive and negative slopes. The momentum may be p at each x point, but now it is associated with a probability which may take one positive and negative values. Given that a particle either translates to the right or to the left, an increasing slope in one direction gives the sense of motion in that direction and the decreasing slope, the opposite direction. This means that for a hump (which is not linked to any overall translation to the right or left), there is internal forward motion followed by internal negative motion. We call this zero point motion. This causes an issue because usually positive and negative signs refer to positive or negative overall translation, but matters are more complicated here. There is an overall translation (either to the left or right) with magnitude p , but this is linked to constant probability at each x point unlike a $\sin(px)$ series of humps which contains both forward and negative p in different regions.

As a consequence it is not possible to describe both zero point forward/negative probability* p motion with no translation and p translation in one direction in one dimension. One is forced to use two dimensions. The usual x -number line describes positive/negative zero point type motion, while an even distribution with an odd distribution in px in a second dimension describes translational motion. The two dimensional set of zero point motions must combine to treat each point the same. Previously we have argued this means that $\text{Probability}(p \text{ translation}) \text{Probability}(-p \text{ translation}) = \text{constant}$. This leads to a two dimensional scheme which describes both zero point motion (which we have argued is linked to impulse) and translation i.e.

$$\exp(ipx) = \cos(px) + i \sin(px) \quad ((1))$$

In other words the positive/negative zero point motion tells one nothing of the direction of translation as $\cos(px)$ is the same for both p and $-p$.

Given $\exp(ipx)$ one may find p , and pp at any x point i.e.

$$p \exp(ipx) / \exp(ipx) = p \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and} \quad pp \exp(ipx) / \exp(ipx) = pp \quad ((2b))$$

Thus at each x point the translational motion appears. The internal $\exp(ipx)$ motion, however, is linked with the details of an impulse interaction i.e. as in 2-slit interference. The idea of mapping $\exp(ipx)$ to x,p is an abstraction.

The Problem with Acceleration

There is an issue, however, in the case of Newtonian acceleration. A particle moving with constant speed already has two distributions $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ and so how does one map $\exp(ip_1x) \rightarrow p_1, x_1$ and $\exp(ip_2x) \rightarrow p_2, x_2$. This cannot really be done unless dx is of the order of magnitude of \hbar/p_1 and also \hbar/p_2 where dx is small compared with the length of say a bound system.

As a result, one has an unusual situation in the case of acceleration. For a constant p , one has both zero point positive/negative motion, and constant translational motion. $\exp(ipx)$. $\exp(ipx)$ is represented by two dimensional probability showing both zero point and translational motion (i.e. the full picture) while $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$ is linked only with translational motion and does not show direction.

Consider next a bound state with a potential $V(x)$ so that one may have a constant energy. In a classical scenario, a particle moves either to the right or to the left, as one may follow it in time. Within a wavelength \hbar/p one does not follow the particle in time and it is possible to have $\cos(px)+i\sin(px)$ and $\cos(-px) + i \sin(-px)$ together. This means that one loses one dimension, the dimension used to describe translational motion. This does not mean that translational motion disappears, the particle is still translating (but one combines forward and negative translational motion). This leaves zero point motion with forward/backward motions linked to the probability distributions $\cos(px)$. How can this give rise to acceleration?

Given that $V(x)$ is present in the problem, taken from classical physics and representing a measurable, one cannot overlook the classical notion of conservation of energy. Thus there should exist a p special(x) such that p special(x) p special (x)/2m = KE(x) classical. P special(x), however, cannot be a constant. Furthermore all that is left is zero point forward/backwards moton linked with the probability $\cos(px)$ and so this probability (linked in the free particle case to zero point motion) now influences translational motion in the bound system through:

$$KE(x) = \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p^2 / \cos(px) \} / \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ \cos(px) \} \ a(p)=a(-p) \quad ((3))$$

$$\text{And } KE(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((4))$$

Thus free motion is governed by the Newtonian values p and $p^2/2m$ at each x point, but a bound state, which in terms of probability includes p and $-p$ translation together, creates an average kinetic energy based strictly on zero point motion probability i.e. $\cos(px)$. In other words, zero point type motion is the driver in a bound system to a large degree, although $V(x)$ is also present and this is linked to translational motion.

What are the consequences of a quantum bound state being strongly influenced by zero point motion? First, $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ \cos(px)$ may have a $\sin(px)$ like form with different heights and base-hump widths. For a free particle, each x point is associated with a constant p and $p^2/2m$, while in the bound case each x point is associated with three values:

$$KE(x) \text{ classical, } p_{rms}(x) \text{ from } KE(x) \text{ and } \langle p \rangle = -i\hbar dW/dx / W \quad ((5))$$

$\langle p \rangle$ is linked with zero point energy which still exists in the bound system, in fact it partially defines the system (together with $V(x)$) in that it is the zero point probability $\cos(px)$ which partially governs the creation of the average $KE(x)$. $\cos(px)$, however, is not the only probability distribution in the system, because one must introduce probability type weights $a(p)$ for the various $\cos(px)$ in order to satisfy the classical constraint:

$$KE(x) + V(x) = E \quad \text{because one uses the classical } V(x) \quad ((6))$$

An important point, we argue, is that $W(x)$ often has humps, i.e. a $\sin(px)$ type form with different heights and widths. This shows the influence of the zero point motion in creating the bound system. The different heights of the humps show the influence of $V(x)$ because the zero point average momentum at these peaks, proportional to dW/dx is 0.

As a result, $KE(x) = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW/dx}{W}$ where $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$. $KE(x)$, however, is of the form of Fisher information at a fixed x (x being the parameter) and p the random variable.

In (1) Fisher information is defined as:

$$E \left[\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} F(p,x) / F(p,x) \mid x \right] \quad ((7))$$

Here x is the parameter (at the point x), p is the random variable and $F=W$ the wavefunction. This is already known in the literature (2).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue there exists an arbitrariness and independence of x and t found in (Newtonian mechanics) and special relativity which may be quantified using the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ to create a distribution for t with a base of \hbar/E and one for x with a base of \hbar/p . If this distribution is symmetric, however, it has positive and negative slopes. Thus if one has a distribution $F(px)$ with F real, an increasing slope suggests motion in one direction and a decreasing slope, motion in the opposite even though p is a constant at each x point i.e. the physical impulse is the same, the probability for it to occur differs. In other words, there is positive/negative zero point motion associated with a deterministic $x=p/m t$.

A first consequence is that a single x axis cannot describe both the positive/negative zero point motion not associated with overall translation, and overall positive/negative translation. In other words, one must introduce two dimensions such that the two dimensional probability describes translation i.e. treats each x point as having the same weight. This leads to $\cos(px) + i \sin(px)$. For a free particle, however, translation may be described by mapping $\exp(ipx)$ to p , $pp/2m$ at every x i.e. Newtonian mechanics.

Such, however, is not the case for acceleration. In order to study acceleration, we consider the case of a bound system. Classically, the particle should accelerate to the right, then turn and accelerate to the left. If the wavelength \hbar/p , however, is comparable with the size of the system, there is a time uncertainty within a wavelength \hbar/p and a particle with p may become

intertwined with $-p$. Thus one has $\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)$ or $\cos(px)$. This is the zero point forward/backwards probability which is not dependent on a specific direction of motion, only its magnitude. If $V(x)$, a classical potential exists, one must impose conservation of energy as there are no sources or sinks. As a result, $V(x)$ AND the zero point probability $\cos(px)$ govern the form of the average kinetic energy which has the appearance of translational energy i.e. $KE(x) = KE(x)_{\text{classical}} = E - V(x) = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W$. $W(x)$ contains both zero point forward/backward motion from $\cos(px)$ and $a(p)$ weights linked to $V(x)$ through $KE(x) + V(x) = E$. In fact, $KE(x)$ is of the form of a Fisher information at x (as is already known in the literature). The influence of the zero point forward-backward motion is clearly seen in the peak/trough pattern of $W(x)$ which yields the spatial density $W^*(x)W(x)$.

In a classical statistical mechanical system $P(p)$ and $P(-p)$ are the same, so $P(p) + P(-p) = 0$. To obtain a density there must be a large number of particles which are shifted in space. In the quantum case, there is already a spatial distribution associated with the so-called point x , i.e. $\cos(px)$ which holds for both p and $-p$. Thus a superposition of zero point probabilities (forward-backward motions) $\cos(px)$'s, with weights $a(p)$, can create the impression of translational kinetic energy. This shows why a bound system with acceleration is associated with a wavefunction of crests and troughs, albeit ones with different heights and widths.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fisher_information
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/B._Roy_Frieden